

EVALUATION OF HEMODIALYSED PATIENTS IN THE EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT : DESCRIPTIVE RESEARCH

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Keywords

Acute renal failure

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ABSTRACT

In our study, we aimed to investigate the demographic data, clinical characteristics and outcomes of patients who were admitted to haemodialysis from the emergency department for any reason. In this study, the demographic data, clinical characteristics, emergency dialysis indication, laboratory values and hospitalisation status of the patients who applied to the emergency department Hatay Mustafa Kemal University, Faculty of Medicine Hospital and for whom emergency haemodialysis was indicated were retrospectively evaluated. Statistical calculations were examined using IBM SPSS 26 software. A total of 127 patients, 59.1% (n=75) of whom were male, were included in our study. The median age of the patients was 67 (55-77) years. Although the complaints on admission varied, the most common complaint was general condition disorder with 19.7% (n=25) and the least common complaint was chest pain (3.1%) (n=4). 37.8% (n=48) of the patients had no comorbidities, 45.7% (n=58) had chronic kidney disease (CKD), 33.9% (n=43) had hypertension (HT). The indication for dialysis was most common in 56.7% (n=72). 7% (n=72) had acute renal injury (AKI). Creatine (Cre) was 5.77 mg/dl (4.36-7.96), blood urea nitrogen (BUN) was 93.50 (mg/dl) (64-128.20). 71.7% (n=91) of the patients were dialysed for the first time, 72.4% (n=92) had catheter insertion under emergency conditions and 47.2% (n=60) of the dialysed patients were hospitalised in intensive care unit. It was observed that the majority of patients who underwent dialysis in emergency departments were due to AKI and the majority of these patients were catheterised and hospitalised in emergency departments.

INTRODUCTION

Emergency departments are the areas where intoxicated patients and patients with acute and chronic renal failure are most frequently evaluated and haemodialysis treatment is applied.

Renal replacement therapy (RRT) is a form of treatment that restores renal function by removing toxins and regulating fluid balance¹. RRT methods consist of 85% haemodialysis, 10% peritoneal dialysis and 5% kidney transplantation². The most commonly used method in our country is haemodialysis³. Haemodialysis is a process based on the removal of solute substances from the body using a dialyser and the removal of solute substances during this process occurs by diffusion or ultrafiltration⁴.

Kidneys play an important role in acid-base regulation. Emergency haemodialysis is a life-saving treatment in certain clinical situations in patients with acute kidney injury (AKI) and chronic kidney disease (CKD). Hypervolemia not responding to treatment, hyperkalaemia resistant to medical treatment, metabolic acidosis and uremic conditions are indications for emergency dialysis⁵. Haemodialysis is the most commonly preferred extracorporeal method for the elimination of some intoxications such as toxic alcohol⁶.

In this study, we aimed to evaluate the patients who were brought to the emergency department and in whom haemodialysis was indicated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted retrospectively in the Hatay Mustafa Kemal University of Medicine Hospital after obtaining hospital permission and ethics committee approval (02/10/2024, No: 11) for 4 years. This study complies with the Declaration of Helsinki was performed.

Demographic characteristics, complaints at admission, clinical features, comorbidities, laboratory data, emergency dialysis indication, whether it was the first dialysis, whether a dialysis catheter was inserted in the emergency department and hospitalisation status were evaluated by scanning

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the hospital data processing system.

Patients over 18 years of age who presented to the emergency department on the specified dates, who were evaluated by emergency physicians and thought to be in need of haemodialysis, and for whom emergency haemodialysis was indicated after consultation with a nephrologist were included in the study.

Statistical analysis

Statistical calculations were performed using IBM SPSS 26 programme. Data were presented by descriptive statistical methods (mean, standard deviation, median, quartiles (25%-75%), frequency, ratio). The conformity of quantitative data to normal distribution was calculated by Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and graphical evaluations. Student-t test was used for comparisons of quantitative data conforming to normal distribution between genders, and Mann Whitney-U test was used for comparisons of non-normally distributed data between genders. Pearson Chi-Square test and Chi-Square Independence Test were used for comparison of unquantifiable data. Significance was accepted as at least $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Our study included 127 patients. The demographic characteristics of the patients are presented in the table below. (Table 1). The most common indication for dialysis was AKI with a rate of 56.7% (n=72). This was followed by patients with routine CKD with 11.8% (n=15), CKD on AKI with 10.2% (n=13), hyperkalemia with 7.9% (n=10), and alcohol poisoning with 4.7% (n=6) (Table 2).

Although admission complaints varied, the most common complaint was general condition disorder with 19.7% (n=25), while the least common complaints were chest pain (3.1%) (n=4), catheter infection (3.1%) (n=4) and diarrhoea (3.1%) (n=4). There were various admission complaints such as nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, inability to urinate, weakness, visual impairment after alcohol use.

While 37.8% (n=48) of the patients had no comorbidity, 33.9% (n=43) had hypertension risk factor. Additional diseases such as prostate and bladder cancer (6.3%) (n=8), kidney stones (2.4%) (n=3), heart disease (7.9%) (n=10), other malignancy (8.7%) (n=11), sickle cell anaemia (5.5%) (n=7) and association of heart disease, HT and DM (3.1%) (n=4) were found (table 3).

When the blood values of the patients were examined, Lactate (lac), mean erythrocyte volume (MCV) values were in the normal range, bicarbonate (HCO_3), haemoglobin (Hb), Ph values were low, creatine (cre), blood urea nitrogen (BUN), potassium (K) values were high (table 4).

HCO_3 bicarbonate, LAC:lactate, BE: base deficit, HB: haemoglobin, MCV:, mean erythrocyte volume, CRE: creatine, BUN: blood urea nitrogen, K: potassium When blood values were analysed in terms of gender. Cre and K values were statistically different in terms of gender; Cre value was higher in male patients ($p=0.031$) and K value was higher in female patients ($p=0.001$); other values were similar (table 5).

DISCUSSION

Haemodialysis is widely used as a life-saving treatment method in emergency departments where patients with acute and chronic renal failure, electrolyte disturbance and poisoning for any reason apply. Dialysis units are now established in many hospitals, and in our hospital, haemodialysis unit is open 24 hours a day and bedside haemodialysis is performed in intensive care units.

Haemodialysis treatment is not seen at the same rate in different age groups and genders. Patients over 65 years of age are more likely to be more predisposed to ABI⁷. In our study, when the study including 127 patients who received haemodialysis from the emergency department was examined, it was seen that most of the patients were male and the mean age was 67 years. The study conducted by Özpölat et al. in Turkey titled Investigation of patients receiving emergency haemodialysis in the emergency department has similarities in terms of age and gender⁸. However, unlike our study, a study in the literature showed that the age group was predominantly between 45-64 years⁹. In other studies similar to our study in terms of gender, it was observed that the male gender progressed to renal failure and the need for dialysis occurred more rapidly, but it is not fully understood whether this is due to biological differences, lifestyle changes, or socioeconomic level differences¹⁰.

When the literature was analysed, it was observed that the most common presenting complaint was dyspnoea, but similar complaints such as nausea and vomiting, confusion and catheter infection were also observed⁸. In our study, it was observed that the most common complaints of the patients presenting to the emergency service were general condition

Table 1. Comparison of Categorical Variables According to Operation Type

		Operation Type				p**
		Laparoscopic*		Open*		
		Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	
Gender	Male	52	91,2	91	85,8	0,455 ^a
	Female	5	8,8	15	14,2	
Side	Unilateral	45	78,9	83	78,3	1,000 ^a
	Bilateral	12	21,1	23	21,7	
Hernia type	Indirect	37	64,9	68	64,2	0,994
	Direct	13	22,8	25	23,6	
Complication	Both	7	12,3	13	12,3	
	Present	10	17,5	12	11,3	0,385 ^a
Complication Type	Absent	47	82,5	94	88,7	
	Bleeding	3	5,3	4	3,8	
Atelectasis	Seroma	2	3,5	5	4,7	
	Organ Injury	1	1,8	0	0,0	
Drain	Atelectasis	4	7,0	3	2,8	
	Present	4	7,0	3	2,8	0,394 ^a
	Absent	53	93,0	103	97,2	
	Present	4	7,0	10	9,4	0,817 ^a
	Absent	53	93,0	96	90,6	

*Column Percentage, ** Pearson Chi-Square Test, ^aYates' Correction for Continuity

Table 2. Comparison of Continuous Variables According to Operation Type

	Group				p*
	Laparoscopic		Open		
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	
Age	35,1	12,2	49,6	15,6	<0,001
Pain	6,4	1,3	3,9	1,5	<0,001
Operation Duration (Minutes)	56,7	25,3	36,8	11,6	<0,001
Length of Hospital Stay (Days)	1,9	1,1	1,2	0,5	<0,001

*Mann Whitney U Test

Table 3. Data on comorbidity

Comorbidity	n	%
No	48	37,8
Dm+Ht	15	11,8
Ht	13	10,2
Malignancy (Other)	11	8,7
Heart Disease	10	7,9
Dm	8	6,3
Prostate And Bladder Cancer	8	6,3
Sickle Cell Anaemia	7	5,5
Dm+Ht+Heart Disease	4	3,1
Kidney Stone	3	2,4
Total	127	100,0

Table 4. Blood values

	mean±SS/median (IQR)
PH	7,2±0,13
HCO ₃ (mmol/L)	13,40(9,50-17,02)
LAC (mmol/L)	1,40(0,90-3,30)
BE (mmol/L)	-12,60±6,69
Hb(g/dl)	9,83±2,70
Mcv(fl)	88,7(83,17-93,35)
CRE(mg/dl)	5,77(4,36-7,96)
BUN(mg/dl)	93,50(64-128,20)
K(mmol/L)	5,60±1,30

Table 5. Comparison of blood values in terms of gender

	Male mean±SS/ median(IQR)	Famale mean±SS/median (IQR)	p
PH	7,21(7,13- 7,30)	7,24(7,10-7,30)	0,632
HCO3	13,80(9,50- 17,60)	12,60(9,27-17,70)	0,899
LAC	1,60(1-4,80)	1,30(0,82-2,20)	0,095
BE	-12,69±6,69	12,47±6,75	0,854
HB	9,95(8,30- 11,72)	9,10(8,20-10,72)	0,179
MCV	88,80(83,82- 92,47)	88,70(81,67-94,65)	0,729
CRE	6,53(4,63- 8,54)	4,99(4,33-6,42)	0,031*
BUN	96(64-130,50)	88(64,10-119,75)	0,705
K	5,27±1,16	6,07±1,36	0,001*

*Independent Samples test, * Mann-Whitney Test, p<0,05*

disorder and dyspnoea, and many complaints such as nausea and vomiting, inability to urinate, weakness, visual impairment, blurred consciousness, catheter infection and chest pain were observed and it was compatible with the literature.

In analyses conducted in the United States of America, DM was observed in 55% of patients with CKD or AKI on dialysis, while HT was observed in 33%¹¹. In contrast, in our study, 37.8% of the patients on emergency dialysis had no comorbidities, while hypertension was observed in the first place in 33.9%, followed by DM, and even DM and HT were seen together in some patients. In the study conducted by Özpolat et al. in our country, HT was found to be more common as a comorbidity, which supports our study⁸.

In a study investigating the gender differences in renal failure and dialysis treatment in Austria, it was found that the mean serum creatinine of male patients on dialysis was higher than that of female patients and it was thought that this was due to the fact that men had more muscle mass¹². In our study, similar to this study, it was observed that creatinine value was higher in male patients.

According to the 2016 National Nephrology, Dialysis and Transplantation Registry System Reports, 66.44% of patients who started dialysis in our country received emergency haemodialysis and the most common indications for dialysis were hypervolemia (40%) and hyperpotassemia (25%)(13). In our study, the indication for dialysis was mostly AKI, while hypervolemia and hyperpotassemia were less common indications. In some cases, CKD patients who are not on

dialysis are urgently dialysed after the development of AKI. In a study by Hsu et al, 1061 CKD patients who did not need haemodialysis needed dialysis and hospitalisation due to AKI¹⁴. In our study, this patient group ranked third among the indications for emergency dialysis. Patients with known CKD may be dialysed under more appropriate conditions with better follow-up.

In the last 50 years, the use of haemodialysis treatments among extracorporeal methods in poisoning has gradually increased. The increase in the importance of haemodialysis treatments in the management of poisoned patients is probably due to the inadequacy of the existing methods, the advancing technology has made haemodialysis treatment more effective in removing toxins and the role of extracorporeal treatments in poisoning will continue to increase over time (15-17). In the United States, the best available data show that extracorporeal therapy is applied in 0.45% of poisoning exposures¹⁵. In different Western countries, ethylene glycol, lithium and salicylates have consistently accounted for approximately two thirds of poisonings treated by extracorporeal method¹⁵. It is recommended that every methyl alcohol intoxication patient who shows signs of severe metabolic acidosis, visual impairment and end organ failure, especially after alcohol intoxication, should be taken to haemodialysis without delay¹⁸. In our study, all of our patients who underwent urgent haemodialysis due to intoxication were found to have alcohol intoxication and these patients presented with visual impairment and patients with severe metabolic acidosis underwent urgent haemodialysis and patients who underwent intensive care were discharged from the hospital after follow-up.

In a study conducted by Özpolat et al. it was observed that 54.2% of the patients receiving emergency dialysis were catheterised in the emergency department⁸. It has been emphasised that insertion of a catheter for dialysis is not a simple procedure and a mistake made may affect the treatment processes of the patients in the following processes, no benefit can be seen again due to damaged vessels and may even cause failure in permanent catheter applications^{19,21}. Therefore, it is recommended that this procedure should be planned in a more appropriate area so as not to harm the patient. In our study, it was observed that 72.4% of the patients were inserted a dialysis catheter in the emergency department.

Performing this procedure under more appropriate conditions may be good for both patients and emergency departments, which are busy enough in our country.

Almost all of the dialysed patients required hospitalisation, and this is thought to be due to the advanced age of the patients and the presence of more than one underlying comorbidity^{22,23}. In our study, all patients were hospitalised. Similar to our study, in a study conducted by Aktepe et al. on patients who were dialysed in the emergency department, it was observed that all patients were hospitalised²⁴.

CONCLUSION

It was observed that renal failure occurs in the elderly population due to many diseases such as DM, HT and heart disease and these patients were urgently admitted to haemodialysis. Haemodialysis treatment may be preferred as a life-saving treatment especially in patients presenting with alcohol intoxication.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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No

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